

POLYARTERITIS NODOSA: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The present study intends to carry out a literature review on polyarteritis nodosa (PAN), with the aim of analyzing the clinical repercussions and therapeutic management of the disease. The research was based on scientific articles in Portuguese and English published between 2010 and 2023, selected from scientific databases such as Pubmed and SciELO that were available in full. The results showed that polyarteritis nodosa is a vasculitis of rare incidence and unknown etiology that causes acute inflammation and fibrinoid necrosis of small and medium-sized arteries. Signs and symptoms can affect different sites, preferably the kidneys, skin, joints, muscles, peripheral nerves and gastrointestinal tract. It is considered a pathology that is difficult to diagnose and treat.

Keywords: Polyarteritis nodosa; Vasculitis; Inflammation.

INTRODUCTION

Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) consists of systemic necrotizing vasculitis, in which acute inflammation and fibrinoid necrosis of small and medium-sized arteries are identified. It is considered a rare disease whose diagnosis is made by clinical and histopathological findings. It progresses with invasion of the blood vessel wall by immune system cells, causing stenosis, occlusion, formation of aneurysms and/or hemorrhages, capable of causing secondary tissue ischemia. There is great variability in signs and symptoms, due to the different sites that can be affected, preferably kidneys, skin, joints, muscles, peripheral nerves and gastrointestinal tract. It has an unknown etiology and is difficult to treat.

GOAL

The present study aims to analyze scientific articles on the repercussions and management of polyarteritis nodosa (PAN).

METHODOLOGY

The exploratory research method was used in this work, through a bibliographic search to obtain references that expand knowledge about polyarteritis nodosa. The research was based on scientific articles in Portuguese and English published between 2010 and 2023, selected from scientific databases such as Pubmed and SciELO that were available in full. For the search, health descriptors relevant to the topic were used, such as: Polyarteritis nodosa, Vasculitis, Inflammation. The exclusion criteria refer to articles that exceeded the stipulated period of time and that are not available in full in the databases searched.

RESULTS

Polyarteritis nodosa is a vasculitis with a rare incidence (4.6/100,000) with a higher prevalence in males, between 40 and 60 years old. Systemic PAN generally begins with fatigue, asthenia, fever, myalgia and arthralgia, then affecting the skin, peripheral nerves, digestive tract and kidneys. Development can be acute and prolonged, insidious, presenting as a chronic and disabling condition, or subacute, if a long period has passed without treatment.

Cutaneous manifestations are rare, affecting dermal and subcutaneous vessels, with unknown etiology. The main skin symptoms are: subcutaneous nodules, livedo reticularis and ulcerations, mainly on the lower limbs.

Gastrointestinal manifestations are called intestinal angina and can be continuous or intermittent, worsening after meals. Other symptoms: nausea, vomiting, melena and diarrhea. These manifestations result from mesenteric arteritis, which predominantly affects the small intestine. Ischemia and perforations can occur in severe cases. The patient may report myalgia and generalized weakness when there is muscle involvement.

The most common neurological change in PAN is mononeuritis multiplex, where motor and sensory deficits are presented. The most affected nerves are the ulnar, radial and peroneal. This condition may be present in up to 70% of patients with the pathology.

The diagnosis must meet at least 3 of the 10 criteria adopted by the American College of Rheumatology: 1) weight loss of more than 4 kg; 2) livedo reticularis; 3) testicular pain or swelling; 4) myalgia; 5) peripheral neuropathy; 6) diastolic blood pressure greater than 90mmHg; 7) elevation of urea and creatinine; 8) positivity for hepatitis B (HBsAg positive); 9) arteriographic abnormalities (aneurysms or occlusions); 10) histopathological changes (granulocytes or granulocytes and mononuclear cells in the arterial wall).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Polyarteritis nodosa is characterized by variable clinical manifestations and evolution, so that it can culminate in rapid-onset arterial hypertension with progression to renal failure. The therapeutic approach aims to reduce the repercussions of the disease, increase patient survival and improve their quality of life. The proposed treatment with corticosteroid therapy and cyclophosphamide is based on the literature and presents a good clinical response. This therapeutic option provides 80% survival in 5 years, to the detriment of those who did not undergo treatment, whose survival rate is 50% in the first year and 13% in the fifth year, respectively.

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